

D10.3. Dissemination & Communication Toolkit

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Document control sheet

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About DELYCIOUS

As Europe accelerates its transition to clean energy, the Net Zero Industry Act identifies low-carbon hydrogen production as a strategic priority. DELYCIOUS tackles key challenges in water electrolysis technology, focusing on extending electrolyzer lifespans and reducing operational costs under variable renewable energy sources. In DELYCIOUS, the development of cost-efficient, innovative, open, universal, and safe diagnostic tools to investigate the chemical and electrochemical properties of electrolysis systems is foreseen. This project combines Raman Spectroscopy (Raman) and Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS), to explore the chemical and electrochemical properties of electrolysis systems. By using both physical and data-driven modeling, it will be possible to identify important degradation parameters. To ensure that the diagnostic tools work effectively in various temperature ranges and across various electrolysis technologies, three technologies namely Alkaline Electrolysis (AEL), Proton Exchange Membrane Electrolysis (PEMEL), and Solid Oxide Electrolysis (SOEL) are addressed in this project, with a demonstration on alkaline electrolyzers beyond 100 KW.

Consortium

Coordinator

**UNIVERSITY
OF TWENTE.**

DUMAREY

HORIBA

etaflorence

 **stargate
hydrogen**

Executive Summary

The purpose of this deliverable is to establish a **cohesive and professional communication framework** for DELYCIOUS, ensuring consistency across all dissemination and outreach activities. It serves as a **comprehensive reference** for project partners, providing essential materials to effectively communicate the project's objectives, progress, and impact to key stakeholders.

By defining the project's **visual identity** and **providing ready-to-use templates**, this toolkit facilitates seamless internal and external communication. Additionally, the inclusion of **an A0 poster and flyer** supports engagement at conferences and industry events, while **social media assets and the project website** help maximize DELYCIOUS's online presence, fostering visibility and stakeholder interaction.

This deliverable ultimately contributes to **enhancing the project's reach and impact**, aligning with the broader communication and dissemination strategy outlined in Work Package 10.

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1. Visual Identity & Project Logo

The DELYCIOUS project logo visually encapsulates its core mission and technological focus. The **color palette**, featuring shades of blue and green, reflects the project's alignment with **hydrogen technologies and sustainability**, symbolizing clean energy and innovation.

The **dominant visual element** is a stylized representation of an **electrolyzer**, seamlessly embedded within the letter "U" shape, reinforcing the project's commitment to advancing electrolyzer diagnostics. Additionally, the **wave-like patterns beneath the letter "Y"** represent **Raman spectroscopy and Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS)**—two key diagnostic techniques used in the project. These elements collectively convey the project's emphasis on **precision monitoring, efficiency, and electrochemical innovation** in hydrogen production.

Figure 1: DELYCIOUS project logo and design element

2. Mandatory Requirement for Dissemination Material

In DELYCIOUS dissemination materials – such as templates, social media page, website, and banners – the Clean Hydrogen Partnership logo and the EU emblem are prominently displayed. Additionally, official acknowledgement of project funding, indicating the project number is featured on the front page, title slide, and other relevant materials.

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Figure 2: CHP logo, EU emblem and funding acknowledgement in different project materials

3. Project Templates

3.1. Deliverable Template

A template in MS docx format is prepared for the presentation of the deliverable reports that can be recycled for other project documents e.g. milestone reports and summaries, if required. This template is stored in our internal communication channel accessible to consortium partners. All partners are encouraged to **use this Deliverable Template** when reporting and documenting their respective deliverables to ensure consistency and compliance with project visual standards. The current deliverable is based on this template.

3.2. Presentation Template

For project presentations a MS ppt template has been prepared and available to all partners for both **internal meetings** and **external representations of DELYCIOUS** to ensure consistency and compliance with project visual standards.

Figure 3: Title slide of the project's PPT template

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4. Social Media and Website

4.1. LinkedIn

LinkedIn serves as the **primary social media platform** for DELYCIOUS, where the project shares **key updates, milestones, and engagement opportunities**. This includes **webinars, conferences, industry news, and project developments**, reaching both **specialized audiences with technical expertise** and the **general public interested in hydrogen technologies**.

Through LinkedIn, DELYCIOUS fosters **collaboration, knowledge exchange, and stakeholder engagement**, ensuring broad visibility and impact within the hydrogen and renewable energy sectors.

Within 3 months of the project kickoff, [the DELYCIOUS LinkedIn page](#) published 4 posts, gaining 131 followers by April 1, 2025. Approximately 6000 impressions (the number of times DELYCIOUS's content is displayed in someone's feed, regardless of whether they interact with it) and 160 post reactions were recorded.

Figure 4: A screenshot of the project LinkedIn page

4.2. Website

The [DELYCIOUS project website](#), which launches on April 2025 serves as the **central hub for information and resources**, featuring key highlights about the project, including its **objectives, expected impacts, innovative technologies, and work plan**. It also provides an overview of the **consortium partners involved** and their respective roles in delivering project outcomes.

In addition to these core elements, the website offers **news updates, upcoming events, published deliverables, and engagement opportunities** such as **webinars and conferences**. Designed to cater to both **technical experts and the general public**, the website ensures **transparency, knowledge dissemination, and stakeholder interaction**, reinforcing DELYCIOUS's impact in the hydrogen and renewable energy domains.

ETA collects general data from website visitors, which is stored in server log files. This includes browser type and version, operating system, referring websites, visited sub-pages, access date and time, IP address, internet service provider, and other technical data related to system security. The data is used for website functionality, optimization and cybersecurity, and legal compliance but is analyzed anonymously without identifying users.

More details on legal and privacy policy can be found here: <https://www.delycious-project.eu/privacy-policy/>

Figure 5: DELYCIOUS Project website

5. Project Introduction Publications

5.1. Roll-up banner

A roll-up banner is a versatile and effective communication tool, ideal for both marketing and informational purposes. It is **printable with 80x200cm dimension, portable and can be displayed in various settings**, from project meeting rooms to high-traffic areas such as exhibitions and conventions. The banner will highlight DELYCIOUS project name, funding, and contact information, ensuring maximum visibility. See in annexure.

5.2. Trifold leaflet

The trifold leaflet offers a **concise yet informative** overview of the DELYCIOUS project, providing essential details in an **easy-to-digest format**. Designed for convenience, it serves as a **takeaway piece** that audiences can reference later. The leaflets will be printed at 21x29.7cm (A4) and distributed to project partners, who will share them at events where they represent the DELYCIOUS project, ensuring broader outreach. See in annexure.

5.3. Digital poster

digital poster is a visually engaging and dynamic representation of the DELYCIOUS project. Designed for **high-resolution digital display**, it will be available on the project website, allowing visitors to quickly grasp key project details at any time, whether on their desktop or mobile devices. This format ensures accessibility and enhances audience engagement with the project's core message. The online dimension is A4; however, the poster can be printed at any size from A5 to A0. See in annexure.

Annexure

This includes Roll-Up Banner, Trifold Leaflet and a Digital Poster.

Diagnostic tools for **ELectroLYsers**:
Cost-efficient, Innovative, Open, Universal
 and **Safe**

ABOUT

Optimizing the Operation of Renewable Hydrogen Production Units

KEY INNOVATIONS

Advanced Diagnostics

Universal Compatibility

Extended Electrolysers Lifetime

PROJECT BUDGET

4 Million €

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

Develop a Flexible Test Platform

Advanced Hardware Sensors

Cutting-Edge Algorithms

Open-Access Software Platform

TARGET STAKEHOLDERS

Electrolyser manufacturer & operators

Renewable energy providers

Investors

Hydrogen associations

Business associations

Academia

Media

Policy makers

CONSORTIUM PARTNERS

KEY ACTIVITIES & WORKPLAN

Project management and coordination

Lab-scale validation of three electrolysis technologies

Hardware Development and Integration

Algorithms

Software Integration

Large-Scale Validation

Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation

TIMELINE

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delycious-project.eu

in DELYCIOUS Project

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Renewable Hydrogen: A Strategic Pillar for Europe's Net-Zero Goals

The **Net Zero Industry Act** highlights green hydrogen as essential for Europe's clean energy future, with hydrogen expected to meet **20% of the EU's energy needs by 2050.**

Powered by renewable energy, **water electrolysis** produces clean, carbon-neutral hydrogen – an energy carrier that can be stored, transported, and converted back to electricity with **water as the only by-product.**

PARTNERS

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DELICIOUS Project

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Diagnostic tools for
Electro**Y**sers:
Cost-efficient,
Innovative, **O**pen,
Universal and **S**afe

6 Strategic Project Objectives

Development of a Flexible Test Platform

Advanced Hardware Sensors

Cutting-Edge Algorithms

Open-Access Software Platform

Large-Scale Demonstration

Roadmap to Commercialization

Innovative Approach

Advanced Diagnostics

Universal Compatibility

Collaborative Expertise

Impact Vision

Contributes to the Outcomes of the Call HORIZON-JTI-CLEANH2-2024.

Enhances electrolyser performance, drives large-scale deployment and standardization, lowers ownership costs, and enables greater renewable energy integration.

Advances SDG 7 (innovating clean hydrogen), SDG 9 (driving industrial progress), SDG 12 (reducing fossil fuel reliance), and SDG 13 (supporting climate action).

Empowers academia, industry, and professionals through R&D, mentorship, and open data access.

Optimizes green hydrogen economics for new projects and upgrades.

DELYCIOUS

Diagnostic tools for ELECTROLYSERS: Cost-efficient, Innovative, Open, Universal and Safe

We optimize the operation of renewable hydrogen production units.

Co-funded by
the European Union

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Project coordinator

